

Obstacles Ofemploying The Differentiated Education Strategy With Gifted Students In Public Education Schools From The Teacher's Perspective

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 21, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Differentiated Education-, Gifted Students, Public Education Schools</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5799766</p>	<p><i>This study dealt with the obstacles to employing the differentiated education strategy with gifted students in public education schools from teacher's perspective, the sample was chosen randomly of (60) male and female teachers. Using the descriptive approach, the results resulted in a medium college degree for the obstacles to employing the strategy of differentiated education with gifted students, and at the level of the sub-domains, they were respectively (obstacles related to the talented student to a medium degree, followed by the obstacles related to the teacher was a medium degree, and then the obstacles related to the curriculum, and the management was a small degree), with statistically significant differences attributed to the variable years of experience and it came in favor of their experience (16 years and above), The researcher recommended the importance of enabling teacher's gifted students to apply the differentiated education strategy through training, educational and development courses.</i></p>

Introduction

The concept of differentiated education was associated with the Declaration of the Rights of the Child, which it recommended differentiated education for everyone, and considering the learner's levels and capabilities, for achieving the highest levels of success and achievement (Aftab, 2015).

Employing the differentiated education strategy is an applying of the principle of fairness, which is restricted in all international agreements, with the right of every individual to have an equal opportunity in a differentiated education, without discrimination referred to the variances in abilities, or social, economic, or cultural level (Elaine, 2015). Thus, differentiated education has received a great deal of care and attention in many international conferences, which stressed the need to consider the differences between students, and the importance of varying teaching curricula and strategies, to prepare students with the best type of learning that suits their characteristics, abilities and interests (Abanmi, 2018). Differentiated education is a process of approximating the content of the curriculum and the methods of its presentation, depend on the characteristics of the different students in one semester, and it is an educational philosophy based on that teachers must adapt their teaching methods depend on the student's levels (Alavinia, & Farhady, 2012).

Gifted students represent the national wealth of any society, they are the future's pillar and the civilization's spirit, so this requires discovering, refining and upgrading their talents by considering student's levels, multi-intelligence, and providing educational programs that are suitable with their talents (Mahmoud, 2020). Also, differentiated education is based on a number of philosophies such as Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences, that emphasizes the differentiation of individuals according to types of intelligence, the social constructivist theory, which sees that the student learns in a social and cultural context, and that the learning process includes cultural and linguistic factors and interactions with others, and the theory of brain-based learning that emphasizes focusing on both sides of the brain and not just one side (Aftab, 2015).

Differentiation refers to adapting the curriculum and structuring the content by providing a set of appropriate educational experiences and activities through the use of acceleration, complexity, depth, challenge, creativity, and abstraction in gifted education. Talented individuals have unique qualities, abilities, interests, demands, and learning styles, and this diversity necessitates diversification in the curriculum provided to them. (Al-Ghamdi, 2019).

It's worth noting that programs based on the care of gifted students are subject to a variety of procedures, including identifying gifted students, developing curricula and activities for them, and assessing their work. The first responsibility lies in implementing the programs. The efficacy of a teacher who teaches gifted students is related to his awareness of their needs and how to meet them, as well as his ability to differentiate the educational experiences provided in the classroom and the use of teaching methods that account for variances (Mahmoud, 2020). This necessitates educational institutions playing a significant and decisive role in addressing these differences, and providing equal opportunities for everyone based on their characteristics in

order to achieve better growth for them, rather than attempting to change them to fit the educational institutions' agenda. Education that is constructed without regard for students' attitudes, desires, or abilities does not produce the desired result. (Al-Harthy, 2019).

Several scientific studies have found a disparity in the quality of education at the Arab country level, due to the fact that educational content provided in educational institutions is unrelated to the diversity of intelligence, learning styles, and abilities of students, which is due to the omission of differences in students' characteristics and preparations, in addition to the use of traditional educational methods and strategies (Al-Ghamdi, Al-Hisban, 2016). According to the (UNESCO) report, indoctrination and one-way education do not foster critical thinking, and teachers' goals have shifted to increasing student test scores rather than focusing on the student themselves (Ismjli, 2018).

Differentiated education is based on a number of principles and foundations, such as the psychological foundations, which are based on the fact that each student has the ability to learn using various educational methods, and that intelligence is diverse and exists in varying degrees for everyone, and that the human brain's mechanism seeks to understand the meanings of the information it receives. Also, learning occurs when an acceptable and realistic challenge is presented, and human nature always strives for achievement and greatness while accepting the differences between oneself and others unconditionally (Aftab, 2015). "Every child has the right to receive high-quality education in keeping with his abilities and characteristics," according to the legal foundations and human rights treaties, "without discrimination based on gender, economic and social status, mental and physical abilities, or other disparities" (Aldossari, 2018). While educational foundations are dependent on the teacher as the coordinator and facilitator of the educational process, this necessitates improving student personal and professional abilities, as well as the ability to satisfy actual demands. And the unwavering notion that the student is at the center of the educational process, and that teaching's noble objective is to help students learn. By focusing on essential ideas and concepts and eliminating unrelated details, the learner will be able to generate meaning, or translate information into knowledge, and will be able to apply it in a variety of scenarios (Bayoumi, El-Gendy, 2018). While the philosophical foundation is founded on the belief that a teacher's effectiveness is based on customizing teaching methods to meet individual differences in students' aptitudes, inclinations, and learning preferences (Brighton, Moon, & Huang, 2015).

The exploratory stage and tribal evaluation are the most important stages in differentiated education, with the goal of determining students' previous requirements and experiences on the subject of the lesson, as well as defining their capabilities, abilities, tendencies, learning patterns, and types of intelligence. Then, based on those stage findings, categories them according to their common qualities. Following that, the teacher defines the goals of teaching and learning, organizes the educational environment in a way that is acceptable for all groups, selects appropriate methodologies, resources, and educational activities, and determines appropriate evaluation methods. Following the implementation of the course, an evaluation and evaluation method is used to assess the learning outcomes (Ismajli, 2018).

Some countries have requirements for selecting teachers for talented student, such as in Singapore, where a teacher must go through numerous interviews to assess his orientation and preparation for work, with periodic follow-up by the Ministry of Education's Talent Department. Following his selection as a gifted teacher, he must participate in a variety of activities over the course of a year in order to gain a basic understanding of basic concepts, emotional needs, curriculum differentiation skills, and appropriate educational curricula, as well as a commitment to attend periodic meetings in the curricula and programs, and enroll in curricula and programs specializing in the gifted. Every year, there is a competition for talent (Robinson, Whaley, 2014).

(Brighton, Moon, & Huang, 2015) identified a set of principles to be used in evaluating the curriculum, the most important of which is that the curriculum is based on students' abilities and needs, and is characterized by diversity in terms of curriculum content in the cognitive and emotional aspects, as well as integration in terms of curriculum content. It is characterized by complexity since it allows for the study of systems, knowledge, principles, and concepts of core theories, and it allows for self-learning. It allows students to learn from their peers and allows knowledge to be transferred through various knowledge courses. It is distinguished by its depth, which allows students to cope with sophisticated ideas, applications, and abilities. Those that share similar skills and interests. The curriculum allows students to have a better understanding of themselves as well as build personal and social values and ideas. The curriculum also gives students the chance to display communication skills through honing their spoken and written communication skills for their ideas. It is defined by the difficulty required in advanced-level items that demand the student to exert effort to comprehend.

Differentiated curriculum is also one of the techniques for matching gifted individuals' cognitive needs in an advanced-level curriculum that is appropriate with their ability in terms of content and procedure. Where he created the groundwork for differentiated learning for exceptional students and highlighted that gifted students' curriculum should be separate from that of their conventional peers (Brighton, Moon, & Huang, 2015), differentiation aims to provide educational experiences that involve placing the student in settings that challenge his skills and are congruent with his preparations, interests, and tendencies in order to raise Learners engaged in the lifetime learning process (Al-Ghamdi, 2019).

Differential education refers to the variety of students' information backgrounds, their ability to learn the subjects they want, and the numerous teaching techniques that are consistent with their inclinations, learning styles, and intelligence kinds. Teachers' involvement in responding to these variables by offering curriculum content in a number of ways is outlined here (Al-Harthy, 2019). Despite the effectiveness of the differentiated education strategy, it was noted that there are a number of obstacles that prevent gifted students' teachers from properly implementing it. These obstacles include an increase in the number of gifted students in one classroom, a reliance on traditional educational methods, and unified education that ignores educational patterns. Furthermore, an emphasis on the cognitive part of the curriculum, as well as overburdening students with homework, kills the spirit of innovation and challenge. This obstructs the implementation of a differentiated education plan. Which is dependent on offering various access points to knowledge that allows people to absorb ideas and convey what they've learned, so the student pushes himself harder than he pushes others (Aldossari, 2018).

Several studies, including this one, have demonstrated the usefulness of differentiated education for pupils (Bayoumi, Al-Jundi, 2018; Aldossari, 2018; Ismajli, 2018). Other research, such as the study (Al-Ghamdi, 2019, Al-Harthy, 2019, Al-Bardini, 2020, Al-Balawi, 2020), revealed obstacles to differentiated education, posing a significant problem for educational institutions. It is not appropriate to teach the same lesson to people with various abilities and characteristics using the same curriculum, methods, and activities, and then expect them to learn the same skills and information at the same time and in the same way.

Questions of the study

- 1- What are the obstacles to employing a differentiated teacher strategy with gifted students in general education schools from the teacher's perspective?
- 2- Are there any statistically differences in the degree of obstacles to employing the differentiated education strategy with gifted students in general education schools from the teacher's perspective due to the level of experience?

Literature review

The Al-Baltan study (2017) aimed to determine the reality of science teachers' application of differentiated education strategies in the Al-Rass educational governorate, using a sample of (108) male and female teachers, and found that the degree of differentiated education application by teachers was moderately high. The ability of the teacher to use a variety of teaching methods and appropriate learning resources is one of the most significant conditions for success in the implementation of differentiated education. The "huge number of burdens given to the designated study classes, to a very large degree," according to the obstacles that prohibit teachers from using individualized education. There were no variations in the degree to which instructors applied differentiated education based on (school stage, scientific specialization, years of experience), and no differences in the degree to which they applied differentiated education based on the variable of training courses.

A study conducted by Ismajli (2018) aimed of identifying the reality of applying differentiated education to (content, process, and product) according to the abilities and needs of each student. The sample of the study consisted of (200) students, (30) teachers, and (30) parents from public and private schools in Kosovo. The results revealed that the understanding and implementation of differentiated education in primary schools was not within the acceptable level, although professional development initiatives have begun to hold many training courses, but there is still much for them to do in order to enable teachers to understand and implement differentiated education effectively in the classroom.

Al-Ghamdi's (2019) aimed to determine the degree of practicing differentiated education to take care of the artistically talented student from the perspective of female teachers. The sample of the study (228) teachers. It showed that the degree of female teachers' practice of differentiated education was medium. With the presence of differences in differentiated education in the content axis attributed to the variable years of experience for the higher level, with no differences for the variables of educational qualification and training courses.

Al-Harthy study (2019) focused on the obstacles to the use of differentiated education strategies in middle and high schools for gifted students from the teacher's perspective, the sample (70) teachers. The findings revealed that teaching method obstacles were of a medium degree, and the domains "the field of evaluation methods, the field of teaching methods, and the field of teaching tools" were all of a medium degree, with differences for the variables of sex, which were in favor of females, and no differences attributed to practical qualification or years of experience.

Al-Balawi's study (2020) aimed at revealing the obstacles to mathematics teachers' use of differentiated education from teacher's perspective, the sample (452) teachers. The results revealed the greatest challenges, which were, respectively (the school environment ranked first and with a high degree, the learner and at a high degree, obstacles in the nature of differentiated education and at a medium degree, obstacles with the teacher and at a medium degree, obstacles in the academic content and at a medium degree).

The study of Al-Bardini (2020) aimed to reveal the degree of obstacles to the differentiated education strategy in teaching Arabic from the teacher perspective in Jordan. The sample (150) teachers. It was revealed that the total degree of obstacles to the use of differentiated education strategy from the teachers' perspective received a medium degree with a grade of (great), and that at the domain level, it was (for administrative obstacles at the highest average and to a large degree, obstacles related to the learner and to a large degree) Obstacles related to the curriculum to a medium degree, obstacles related to the teacher to a medium degree).

Methods

The descriptive approach was utilized to meet the study's objectives by creating a questionnaire to collect data on the barriers to using a differentiated education strategy with gifted students in public schools.

The sample of the study

The current study's sample included all instructors of gifted students in Jeddah, who numbered (312) at government schools related with the Ministry of Public Education, during the first semester of 2021 AD, and the study was applied to a simple random selection of (60) gifted children teachers.

The statistical description of the sample of the study:

First: Classifying the sample of the study according to the variable years of experience

Table (1): Distribution of sample of the study participants according to the variable years of experience

Years of experience	Number	percentage
(5-10) years	20	33.3
(11-15) years	20	33.3
16 years and above	20	33.3
total	60	100.0

The instrument of the study:

Following an examination of a variety of educational literature, as well as a literature review pertinent to the current issue (Al-Bardini, 2020; Al-Balawi, 2020; Al-Harithi, 2019, Al-Ghamdi, 2019). The researcher created a scale to measure the hurdles to using the differentiated education technique with gifted students in public schools to meet the study's objectives, and it consisted of (22) items dispersed on four primary dimensions represented by:

- The first dimension: obstacles related to the talented student and includes (7) paragraphs.
- The second dimension: obstacles related to the teacher and includes (6) paragraphs
- The third dimension: obstacles related to the curriculum and includes (5) paragraphs
- The fourth dimension: Obstacles related to management and includes (4) paragraph

The examinee responds to the scale items by selecting one of the four options (to a large degree / to a moderate degree / to a small degree / to a very small degree) according to the Likert four-way system of alternatives to measure the obstacles to using the differentiated education strategy with gifted students.

Scale correction

To correct the study of instruments, the Quadrilateral Likert scale was used, which assigns each of its paragraphs one of five degrees (to a big degree/ to a moderate degree/ to a small degree/ to a very low degree) and represents them digitally (4, 3, 2, 1) For the sake of assessing the results using the Likert quadrilateral scale, the following scale was used:

Table No. (2) Classification of the categories of the Quadruple Likert Scale (the limits of the average responses)

M	Category	Category limits
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		From	to
1	Big degree	3.26	4
2	Moderate degree	2.51	3.25
3	Small degree	1.76	2.50
4	Very low degree	1	1.75

It should be emphasized that after statistically processing the average replies of the study sample participants, the length of the range is utilized to reach an objective assessment on them.

Validity:

-The apparent honesty of the instrument of the study (the honesty of the arbitrators):

The scale's apparent validity was confirmed by presenting it to a panel of six arbitrators with expertise in special education, who evaluated the scale's quality in terms of its ability to measure what it was designed to measure and its relevance to the study's objectives, as well as the clarity of each phrase, its connection to its axis, and its importance. And express their opinion on any changes, deletions, or additions to the phrases, and the paragraphs that were authorized by (80%) or more of the arbitrators for suitability were approved, the necessary changes were made, and the scale was taken out in its final form.

-The validity of the internal consistency of the instrument:

To test the instrument's internal consistency, a pilot sample of (30) talented student teachers was chosen from outside the main study sample, and the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient was calculated using the data. This was done to determine the degree of correlation between each of the scale's expressions and the total score of the scale.

Table No. (3) Pearson's correlation coefficients for the scale expressions with the total degree of the scale

Obstacles to employing a differentiated education strategy with gifted students in the intermediate stage from the teacher's perspective				
Dimension	Item number	Correlation coefficient	Item number	Correlation coefficient
First dimension: obstacles related to the talented student	1	**0.716	5	**0.661
	2	**0.514	6	**0.498
	3	**0.621	7	**0.752
	4	**0.621	-	-
The second dimension: obstacles related to the teacher	8	**0.539	11	**0.682
	9	**0.598	12	**0.735
	10	**0.635	13	**0.589
The third dimension: Obstacles related to the curriculum	14	**0.598	17	**0.874
	15	**0.890	18	**0.645
	16	**0.499	-	
Fourth dimension: Obstacles related to management	19	**0.506	21	**0.579
	20	**0.769	22	**0.582

****Significant at level 0.01 or less**

Table (3) shows that the correlation coefficients of each phrase with the total score are positive and statistically significant at the significance level (0.01) or less, indicating the sincerity of the internal consistency of the scale's statements and their suitability to measure what they were prepared to measure.

Reliability

The reliability of the study instrument was confirmed by using Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha (α)), and Table No. (4) Shows the values of Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients.

Table No. (4) Cronbach's alpha coefficient to measure the reliability of the study instrument

Dimension	Item number	Dimension reliability
The first dimension: Obstacles related to the gifted student	7	0.839
he second dimension: obstacles related to the teacher	6	0.911
The third dimension: Obstacles related to the curriculum	5	0.842
The fourth dimension: Obstacles related to management	4	0.863
General reliability	22	0.857

Table No. (4) Shows that the general Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient is high, reaching (0.857), indicating that the scale has a high degree of reliability that can be relied upon in the study's field application, and that the reliability coefficient is high for each dimension of the scale.

A- Half- segmentation method:

The scale items were divided into two groups (odd-numbered items and even-numbered items), the correlation coefficient was calculated between the scores of the odd-numbered items and the scores of the even-numbered items, and the correlation coefficient was corrected in the even-dimensions dimensions using the Spearman-Brown equation. The two portions of the paragraphs are unequal. The Guttman equation was used to produce the findings reported in Table (5).

Table No. (5) Shows the results of the split-half method to measure the reliability of the scale

Dimension	Item number	Dimension reliability
The first dimension: Obstacles related to the gifted student	7	0.864
he second dimension: obstacles related to the teacher	6	0.905
The third dimension: Obstacles related to the curriculum	5	0.879
The fourth dimension: Obstacles related to management	4	0.893
General reliability	22	0.885

It is clear from Table No. (5) That the general reliability coefficient is high, reaching (0.885), and this indicates that the scale has a high degree of reliability that can be relied upon in the field application of the study

The final instrument of the study

In its final form, the scale has (22) items distributed across four dimensions, including (obstacles related to the gifted student, (7) items related to the teacher, (6) items related to the curriculum, (5) items related to administration, and (4) paragraphs.

Statistical analysis:

The data was processed by using the Statistical Package for Social Science "SPSS", using a computer, to answer questions and test hypotheses in the following ways:

- Frequencies, and percentages; In order to identify the characteristics of the study sample participant s
- Weighted mean; to identify the mean responses of the study sample participant s to each of the dimensional phrases, and to arrange the phrases according to the highest weighted average.
- Mean; to find out how high or low the responses of the sample of the study participant s are from the main dimensions.
- Standard Deviation; to identify the extent of the deviation of the responses of the sample of the study participant s to each of the expressions of the study variables, and for each of the main dimensions from its mean.

- Mann-Whitney Test for two independent samples; to identify the differences between the trends of the sample of the study according to their variables, which are divided into two categories of data that do not follow a normal distribution.
- The Kruskal Wallis Test for two or more independent samples; In order to identify the differences between the trends of the sample of the study according to their variables, which are divided into more than two categories of data that do not follow a normal distribution.

Results and discussion

Question one: What are the obstacles to employing a differentiated teacher strategy with gifted students in general education schools from the teacher's perspective?

To determine the obstacles to employing the differentiated education strategy with gifted students, the mean score and the relative weight of these dimensions were calculated in order to determine the obstacles to employing the differentiated education strategy with gifted students, and Table (6) shows the general results of this question.

Table No. (6) Shows the replies of a sample of study participants on a scale of obstacles to using a differentiated education technique with gifted students in the intermediate stage from the teacher's perspective

#	Domains of measurement	Mean Score		Standard deviation	Ranking
		Mean	Level		
1	Obstacles related to the gifted student	3.0976	average	-60751	1
2	obstacles related to the teacher	2.5889	average	-49808	2
3	Obstacles related to the curriculum	2.2833	few	-38142	3
4	Obstacles related to management	2.2458	few	-50734	4
	Obstacles to employing a differentiated education strategy with gifted students in general education schools from the teacher's perspective	2.6189	average	-27921	

According to the findings, the level of obstacles to using the differentiated education strategy with gifted students in public schools was on the mean score (2.6189), or to a moderate degree according to the study's relative criterion. The results showed that (obstacles related to the talented student) reached an average (3.0976), which is in the first order among the dimensions of a scale, at an average level, followed by the dimension (obstacles in the teacher) with an mean score (2.5889), which is also at an average level, followed by the dimension (Obstacles related to the curriculum) reached an average of (2.2833), which is of a small degree, and finally it was found that (obstacles related to management) were with an average of (2.2458), which is of a small degree and in the last place among the dimensions of the scale.

The findings revealed that the challenges faced by gifted students were ranked in the first order on a scale of one to ten. This could be owing to a shortage of general education institutions willing to implement a differentiated education plan based on the student's preparations, interests, and participation in various educational activities (Elaine, 2015). Another obstacle is the rise in the number of gifted students in the classroom, which has resulted in a lack of focus on providing them with research and self-learning skills, as well as a large amount of homework, which limits their creative abilities, and a lack of recourse to a comprehensive assessment of personality aspects, resulting in a low appreciation of creative production. The result is similar with the findings of (Ismajli, 2018; Al-Ghamdi, 2019; Al-Harthy, 2019), although it differs from the findings of (Ismajli, 2018; Al-Ghamdi, 2019; Al-Harthy, 2019). (Al-Bardini, 2020; Al-Balawi, 2020). With regard to the obstacles related

to the teacher, they ranked second and at an average level. It may be due to the fact that the majority of teachers of gifted students assume that gifted students have high intelligence and distinct skills, and therefore they do not need forms of differentiation teaching, which leads to neglecting the needs of students on the social, emotional and academic levels. Moreover, the large number of responsibilities placed on the teacher in preparing practical and technical activities, and the low knowledge of the nature and nature of the differentiated education strategy, instead some teachers resort to the adoption of traditional teaching methods, and the effort and time required for the planning and implementation of the strategy represent major obstacles for the teacher and the result agrees with A study (Al-Harthy, 2019; Al-Ghamdi, 2019; Al-Bardini, 2020; Al-Balawi, 2020). And it varies with the results of the Baltan study, 2017)

On the level of curriculum obstacles, it came to a minor degree, which could be due to a lack of curricula for gifted students that simulate the spirit of challenge and passion for learning, with limited activities that develop higher-order thinking skills and thus a total focus on the cognitive aspect of the curriculum, and thus the result differs from the study (Al-Bardini, 2020), In terms of administrative obstacles, the lack of developmental and educational programs in the differentiated education strategy and its employment mechanism, with limited capabilities and resources, which in turn leads to the low availability of educational and technical aids to the success of employing differentiated education, which came to a moderate degree. The outcome differs from the study's findings (Al-Bardini, 2020, and Al-Balawi, 2020).

Question two: Are there any statistically differences in the degree of obstacles to employing the differentiated education strategy with gifted students in general education schools from the teacher's perspective due to the level of experience?

The researcher conducted the Tests of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk Test) to examine the moderation of the data in the relatively small numbers in the variable years of experience in relation to the total degree and the sub-axes, because most of the parametric tests require that the data distribution be normal, and because the sample number in all Categories was relatively small. The distribution of the data was not moderate for the total score and for all the axes, and to test this hypothesis, the researcher used the Kruskal Wallis Test for two or more independent samples of data that do not follow a normal distribution to compare the average ranks of the sample scores in the total score and in the four dimensions in the obstacles to employing the education strategy. The difference with the gifted students in the intermediate stage from the teacher's perspective is due to years of experience, and the results were as illustrated in the following table.

Table (7): The Kruskal Wallis Test to reveal the significance of the differences in the obstacles to employing the differentiated education strategy with gifted students at the intermediate stage from the teacher's perspective due to years of experience

Dimension	Years of experience	Number	Average rank	Chi square test	sig	Statistical significance
Obstacles related to the gifted student	(10-5)	20	36.58	5.898	0.052	Not statistically significant
	(11-15)	20	23.50			
	16 years and above	20	31.43			
Obstacles related to the teacher	(5-10)	20	31.78	8.219	0.016	statistically significant
	(11-15)	20	22.13			
	16 years and above	20	37.60			
Obstacles related to the curriculum	(5-10)	20	28.05	0.979	0.613	Not statistically significant
	(11-15)	20	33.38			
	16 years and above	20	30.08			
Obstacles related to management	(5-10)	20	35.65	4.145	0.126	Not statistically significant
	(11-15)	20	24.73			
	16 years and above	20	31.13			
The total degree of	(5-10)	20	33.20	7.097	0.029	statistically significant

obstacles	(11-15)	20	22.20			
	16 years and above	20	36.10			

It is clear from the results shown in Table (7) the following:

First: With regard to the total degree of obstacles to employing the differentiated education strategy with gifted students in the intermediate stage from teacher's perspective:

The value of (Sig) for the total degree of obstacles to using the differentiated education strategy with gifted students in public schools was found to be 0.029, which is less than the level of significance (α), indicating that there are statistically significant differences in the degree of obstacles to using the differentiated education strategy with students at the level (α). Years of experience are credited to talented people. The most significant disparities are clearly in favor of the experience category (16 years and up), which received the highest average rank.

The findings revealed that the degree of differences in the obstacles to using the differentiated education strategy with gifted students was in favor of the experience category (16 years and above), owing to the fact that teachers with extensive experience have honed their skills over time and are better able to identify differences between students and classify appropriate educational styles according to each group's inclinations and interests (Al-Bultan, 2017, Al-Harithi, 2019).

Recommendations:

- 1-Providing teachers of gifted students with appropriate knowledge of the differentiated education technique, including what it is and how to use it, through training, educational, and development courses.
- 2-Upgrading the educational process in accordance with the differentiated education strategy and focusing on the differences of pupils rather than on information overload.

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